

carboxaldehyde (0.95 g) and anthranilic acid (1.317 g) or β -alanine (0.89 g) was refluxed for half an hour. The solution was filtered hot, concentrated and cooled to give tobacco-coloured crystals of H_2PB or dark red crystal of H_2PP . m.p. 180° (H_2PB). 120° (H_2PP).

Metal Complexes: These were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the metal acetate (0.005 mole in 10-15 ml 80% ethanol) and H_2PB or H_2PP (0.005 mole in 30-50 ml 80% ethanol) on a steam-bath for 2-4 hours. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised. The pyridine adducts of these complexes were obtained by the method reported earlier⁸.

Based on elemental analysis and molecular weight data the metal complexes and their pyridine adducts display 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry and may possess the composition $[MLX_n]$, where M = metal-ion, X = H_2O or pyridine and $LH_2 = [C_{12}H_{10}N_2O_2]$ or $[C_8H_{10}N_2O_2]$. Thermogravimetric analyses of these complexes show a weight loss compared to three water molecules ($n=3$) when M = Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II), two water molecules ($n=2$) when M = VO^{2+} and one water molecule ($n=1$) when M = Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) or UO_2^{2+} .

The magnetic moments indicate the presence of 4, 3, 2, 1 and 1 unpaired electrons in Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and VO^{2+} complexes and their pyridine adducts respectively and the remaining complexes were found to be diamagnetic. From these values it is apparent that spin-spin interaction does not occur in these complexes and they exist as monomers. The electronic spectra of the complexes supported by the magnetic data suggest nearly octahedral structure for the Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and VO^{2+} complexes and a square-planar stereochemistry for the Pd(II) complexes. Negligibly small ($4.9-9.2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) conductance values of the compounds suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The I.R. spectra of H_2PB and H_2PP consist of bands in the regions $3320-3180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $2570-2560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1695-1680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1660-1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu N-H$, $\nu COOH$, $\nu C=O$ and $\nu C=N$, respectively. In the metal complexes the bands in the region $2570-2560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappeared suggesting coordination through the carboxylate group. $\nu C=N$ of H_2PB and H_2PP was shifted to lower frequency side due to complexation. The appearance of two new bands in the regions $670-640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $600-580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes suggest M-O and M-N bonds formation. All the complexes indicate one broad band at around 3400 cm^{-1} due to νOH of water molecule present.

Thus it is apparent that the general similarity in the complexes of the two ligands is due to the presence of the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in β -position to the carboxylic group. This

result is also in agreement with the findings of Kubo⁴.

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References

1. R. K. GUPTA and R. K. MEHTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **11**, 56.
2. P. PFEIFFER, W. OFFERMANN and H. WERNER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1942, **159**, 313.
3. R. K. MEHTA, S. P. RAO and R. C. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 933.
4. M. KUBO, Y. KURODA, M. KISHITA and Y. MUTO, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, **16**, 7.

Potentiometric Studies on Ternary Complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II)

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THE binary complexes of some bivalent metals such as Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} or Pb^{2+} with picolinic and quinaldonic acids¹ have been studied and the stability constants of metal picolinates reported². Martell et al^{3,4} carried out studies on the ternary complexes of Cu^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with 8-HQS as one of the ligands and heterocyclic base or aminopoly-carboxylic acid as the other ligand. The review of the literature, however, reveals that no investigations on the ternary system of Zn(II) and Cd(II) involving oxine-5-sulphonic acid have been carried out. In the present communication the results on the potentiometric studies of the ternary systems: Zn(II)/Cd(II)-8.HQS-HA (where 8-HQS = 8-hydroxyquinoline, 5-sulphonic acid; HA = quinaldonic acid (QUINA) or picolinic acid (PIC)) have been discussed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR BDH grade. Stock solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardized by their usual methods (Zinc as $ZnNH_4PO_4$ and cadmium as $Cd(C_7H_6O_2N)_2$). The ligand solutions were prepared by direct weighing. All the titrations were carried out in duplicate at temperature $35 \pm 1^\circ$ keeping total volume (50 ml), concentration ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$ in metal or ligand) and ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) constant at the beginning of the titration. pH measurements were made with Philips precision pH meter (PR 9405M) using standard glass and calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

A sharp inflection at $m=1$ in the case of 8-HQS

(curve a), QUINA (curve b) and PIC indicates the neutralisation of the phenolic proton of 8-HQS and carboxylic proton of QUINA and PIC. (m = moles of base added per mole of ligand)

Curve c exhibiting the titration of 1:1 Zn(II)-8-HQS system, indicates an appreciable lowering in pH and an inflection at $m=1$, which may be ascribed to the addition of the ligand to the metal ion resulting in the formation of 1:1 Zn(II)-8-HQS complex. The formation of a solid phase at $m \sim 1$ and another inflection at $m \sim 2$ may, probably, be due to the disproportionation of the initially formed 1:1 complex into 1:2 complex and metal hydroxide.

The curve d represents the titration of 1:1 Zn(II)-QUINA system. An inflection at $m=1$ and an appreciable lowering in pH from the beginning of the titration, indicate the formation of 1:1 Zn(II)-QUINA chelate which is precipitated out from the very beginning. This is in conformity with the earlier observations reported in the literature¹. The change in the appearance of the precipitate from crystalline to gelatinous on adding more of alkali and another inflection at $m \sim 2$ indicate the disproportionation of the initially formed 1:1 complex into 1:2 complex and metal hydroxide.

Except that the formation of solid-phase occurs at $m > 1$ the formation of 1:1 Zn(II)-PIC complex and its subsequent disproportionation into 1:2 binary complex and metal hydroxide may be evidenced by the identical nature of the inflections observed during the titration of 1:1 Zn(II)-QUINA mixture also.

The curve e represents the titration of 1:1:1 Zn(II)-8-HQS-QUINA system. In the lower pH range the curve e runs in between the curve c and curve d up to $m \sim 1$ indicating the formation of the metal complex with both the ligands separately⁶. After $m=1$ the curve e, however, runs outside the curve c and curve d resulting in a single well-defined inflection at $m=2$. This may, possibly be attributed to the formation of a biligand species by the interaction of the two binary species present in equilibrium initially according to the expression

Fig. 1

The biligand species, however, undergoes disproportionation at the higher pH 1:1:1 Zn(II)-8-HQS-PIC system shows similar inflections, the only difference being in the appearance of solid phase at $m \sim 1$ in the latter case.

Observations on 1:1:1: Cd(II)-8-HQS-QUINA/PIC systems are identical to that of 1:1:1 Zn(II)-8-HQS-QUINA/PIC systems.

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References

1. KRINOSUKE SUZUKI, MOTOO YASUDA and KAZUO YAMASAKI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 229.
2. P. O. LUMME and SUOMEN KEMISTILETHI, 1957, **30B**, 182.
3. G. A. L. HEUREUX and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28** 481.
4. C. H. CAREY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2859.
5. K. LAL and R. P. AGARWAL, *J. Less. Common Metals*, 1967, **12**, 269.

The Probable Mechanism of Condensation of Some Reported Heteropoly Niobates and Tantalates in Basic Medium

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THE general principle of condensation process^{1,2} of heteropoly acids is, that the maintenance of acid medium is a must. The mechanism of such condensation process has been established³ successfully through oxobridge idea. But our previous reports^{3,4} reveal a very interesting phenomenon that the condensation of heteropoly niobates and tantalates may take place in basic medium also. The formations of 12-heteropoly Niobotungstate(VI)³ and tantalato tungstate(VI)⁴ have been marked in basic medium^{3,4,5} at some certain pH values 11.5 and 11.6 respectively. Dale et al⁶ has prepared sodium 12-niobotantalatomanganate(VI) at pH 12. In this communication attempts have been made to elucidate some probable mechanism for such types of basic medium condensation process in heteropoly niobates and tantalates.

The example of condensation or polymerization process in basic medium, i.e., in presence of OH ions or groups are numerous in chemical literature. The formation of polynuclear cobalt and chromium complexes through hydroxyl bridge, have been discussed⁷. The closed packed three dimensional crystalline growth of various metal hydroxides through OH groups or ions have been elaborately discussed⁸. There are examples of organic polymers also, wherein, OH groups or ions behaves as catalyst in polymerisation processes. The reaction mechanism in condensation process in organic and inorganic compounds in presence of OH groups or ions may broadly be classified as follows :

(i) Typical structure of OH ions where there is no hydrogen bonding. Examples—aluminium silicates, hydroxides of rare earths, etc.

(ii) Typical coordination of OH group with hydrogen bonding (O-H...O) amongst groups of OH or water molecules. Examples—ice, Conc. H₂SO₄.

(iii) Typical coordination of OH groups without hydrogen bonding⁹. Directed bonds are formed when the groups are attached to different metal atoms, leading to more open packing. In such cases OH-OH distance is generally more than 2.80 to 2.90 Å. The polarization of OH group is not ruled out.

(iv) Typical catalytic behaviour of OH group as in the base catalysed aldol condensation.

For a comparison and prediction with the existing data which is also very scanty, it may be argued that the possibility of the points (iii) and (iv) may be useful to interpret the formation of niobotungstate(VI) in basic medium. A reference to a X-ray examination of isopoly dodecatungstate compound has confirmed the formula to be Na₁₀·[W₁₂O₃₆(OH)₁₀].23H₂O. This shows that the hydrogen present in the compound is not as H⁻ but as OH⁻. The existence of OH group has been further confirmed by n.m.r. spectra⁹. Taking this analogy it may be concluded, that the heteropoly salts of niobotungstate(VI) and tantalatungstate(VI) may contain OH group and this is possible in reaction where there is hydroxyl groups. This prediction needs confirmation by detailed studies of X-ray and n.m.r. spectra. The next possibility of formation is the presence of OH group according to the observation no. (iv). It may be predicted that OH behaves as catalyst and the resultant arrangement might be the polyhedra of the oxides of niobium and tantalum by the elimination of H₂O molecule. Indications may be had from the reports of X-ray studies on isopoly anion [Nb₆O₁₉]⁸⁻, wherein Lindqvist¹⁰ and others pointed out a sort of projection pattern from niobium and oxygen.

References

1. S. K. ROY and G. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 368 ; 1976, **53**, 1076.
2. H. J. EMMEUS and J. S. ANDERSON, 'Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry E. L. B. S., London, 1960, 317-25.
3. G. C. BHATTACHARYA and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1151.
4. G. C. BHATTACHARYA and S. K. ROY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 41.
5. S. K. ROY, Ph.D. Thesis, Ranchi University, 1973.
6. W. B. DALE, J. M. BUCKLEY and M. T. POPE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **2A**, 301.
7. J. C. BAILLER, 'Inorganic Chemistry of Coordination Compounds', Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1965, pp. 23, 452, 453.
8. A. F. WELLS, 'Structural Inorganic Chemistry', Oxford, 1962, pp. 348-553.
9. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, 'Advanced Inorganic Chemistry', Wiley Eastern Private Ltd., New Delhi, 1966, p. 941.
10. I. LINDQVIST, *Ark. Kemi*, 1953, **5**, 247 ; 1954, **7**, 49.